

COMPARATIVE EVALUATION OF SURGICAL TREATMENT OF RECONSTRUCTIVE OPERATIONS FOR THE ELIMINATION OF COLONIC STOMAS IN THE COMPARED GROUPS

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7336784>

According To Statistical Data, The Frequency Of Csc Reaches 50-60%, Among Other Forms Of Colonic Obstruction It Is 10-15%. In The Structure Of Mortality, Wgw Occupies One Of The First Places, Accounting For 4.3-18.9%, And Among The Elderly And Senile - Up To 36.0%. Up To 65% Of Emergency Operations On The Colon End With The Formation Of A Colostomy. At The Same Time, Full Recovery Is Possible Only In 30-40% Of Patients. It Is Well Known What Suffering Patients With Intestinal Stoma Suffer. In Particular, They Are In Constant Psycho-Emotional Stress, And Are Also Significantly Limited In The Physical Plane. Therefore, The Desire Of This Contingent To Get Rid Of Stoman Carriers As Soon As Possible Is Understandable.

Our Data Indicate That The Formation Of A Combined T-Shaped Stoma With Colo-Colonostomy, Due To Extraperitoneal Access, Has A Number Of Advantages Compared To Hartmann's Operations.

This Was Confirmed By A Significant Difference In The Performance Of Restorative Operations At An Earlier Date, As Well As In The Occurrence Of A Significantly Lower Frequency Of Life-Threatening Complications And Mortality. Thus, The Frequency Of Specific Complications Associated With The Technique Of Reconstructive Surgery In The Comparison Group Occurred In 9.7% With A Fatal Outcome In 2.4% Of Patients, While In The Main Group - Only In 5.9%, But Without Fatal Outcomes. At The Same Time, The Frequency Of Nonspecific Complications, In General, In The Comparison Group Occurred In 17.0% With A Fatal Outcome In 2.4% Of Patients, While

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Acute Obstruction Of The Colon Occurs In 29-62.9% Of Cases And Today Is One Of The Most Severe Complications In Tumor Diseases Of The Left Half Of The Colon And Volvulus Of The Sigmoid Colon In Urgent Surgery. In This Area, Scientific Research Continues To Be Carried Out In Clinics And Laboratories Of Our Republic, As Well As In The Cis Countries And Far Abroad. *The Urgency Of The Problem Is Due To The Annual Growth Of Tumor Diseases Of The Colon (3-4 Times), As Well*

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As Postoperative Purulent-Septic Complications (38.6-80%) With A 5-Year Life Expectancy In The Range Of 43.3-55% And High Postoperative Mortality. (Ranges From 16.0 To 52%).

Conclusion. The Use Of An Improved Method For The Formation Of A Combined T-Shaped Stoma With Cololoanastomosis Significantly Facilitates The Performance Of The Reconstructive And Restorative Stage By Extraperitoneal Access, Which Minimizes The Frequency, And Most Importantly, Eliminates The Occurrence Of Life-Threatening Complications And Mortality (Postoperative Complications Associated With The Technique Of Reconstructive Surgery In The Main Group Were Noted Only In 5.9%, But No Deaths).

